

The Multiple Roles of Teacher and Teacher Training in Pakistan

Author's Detail: Muhammad Akram, Najran University, Najran, KSA

Abstract

The role of teacher has been revolutionized in the modern era. The stick and rod culture now has been replaced by the use of modern technology in teaching. This paper highlights the multiple roles of school teachers and teacher training in Pakistan. Teachers fail to add to the confidence of the students. Teachers are not familiar with classroom methodology just because of lack of proper teacher training modules and the use of modern technology in teaching. We have to diagnose the role of teacher in good teaching because teacher is considered to be a pivot in teaching learning process. The present study highlights the current problems faced by a teacher in particular Pakistani context. The study highly recommends that the teacher's role should be clearly determined in order to have a quality learning teaching environment.

Keywords: Teachers' Role, Teacher Training, Teacher Education, Menial Jobs.

Introduction

Both learning and teaching are more than an art. It has been commonly observed that most of the teachers join this profession not by choice but by chance particularly in Pakistani context. The teacher always remains depressed because he does not find any special recognition in the society in which he lives. The multiple roles of teacher are being utilized in consensus, election duties, and referendums and even in social campaigns of basic health programmes. His personal recognition as teacher is always falsified by assigning different extra duties to him. Most of a teacher's time is spent in these other than curricular activities. He does not enjoy any sound social status like other public servants of the society. So it becomes very difficult for a teacher to justify his job because all of these problems are always like an extra burden on the teacher. It is our dilemma that highly qualified teachers are recruited in teaching at primary level and even after that they are forced by the authorities to do these menial jobs.

According to Saeed *et al.* (2013) teacher is one of the factors which influence the proper learning teaching process. Teacher is an important part of the teaching and learning process that faces various problems due to which he cannot play his role effectively in the education process. Teachers are less motivated towards teaching profession, because of so many interruptions in their professional skills. In their study Saeed *et al.* (2013) found that teachers are overburdened with more classes due to shortage of staff in schools, teachers face shortage of teaching and learning

resources in schools, there are fewer professional development opportunities for teachers.

According to Rehman (2002) teaching is considered the most respectful professions in all societies of the world. In other countries of the world teaching is supposed to be the most honorable and lucrative profession but in Pakistani society, teaching does not enjoy a sound social status. Teaching is not considered as an esteemed profession. It is a pity that most of the educated youth comes to this profession when they do not find any other opportunity of lucrative jobs. The least option for the youth remains to be a 'school master' (teacher) or sometimes the 'molvi' (prayer leader).

Effective teachers need to be effective learners as well. However, the professional development of teachers has not been given any proper attention in Pakistan. Resultantly, teachers are found weak in solving students' academic and social problems (Saeed *et al.* 2013).

Ahmed (2012) has examined the interplay between historical legacy, culture and initial teacher education/training policy and actual practice in Pakistan. The philosophy of teacher education starts with the problem of trainee entrants initially but concerns itself with their expected roles, their educative process, expected professional standing, and with the processes of activities encompassing the two major disciplines, pedagogy and psychology along with the development of the personalities of the prospective teachers (Yogesh and Nath, 2008 cited in Ahmed 2012).

The quality of teacher training programmes has an imbalance as they lack harmony with the school system and need to improve by revising the curriculum according to the needs of changing culture and the demands of the modern world (Ahmed, 2009).

According to Ahmed (2012), a full programme of pre-service teacher education includes common courses, disciplinary courses, education specialization courses, and one and a half month or more teaching practicum. Those who meet the programme requirements and pass the examination for teacher qualification obtain a diploma/degree. These courses prepare student teachers to teach common subjects in primary (classes 1-5) and middle (classes 6-8) schools, and this kind of training is not subject-specific. The Draft of National Education Policy (2009) states that:

‘The education sector has been without a comprehensive vision for far too long. Indeed, there have been policies, plans, reforms, goals, objectives, initiatives, and countless vision statement, but there has been no vision; no widely owned understanding of where all of our efforts are taking us; no well informed conception of what a high-quality, high efficiency education system looks like and how it must function in order to be that way’. (P.56)

According to Javed, et al (2012), “the Punjab Education Foundation (PEF) Pakistan has taken initiative for Teachers Training for private sector schools under public private partnership

scheme PEF is playing its pivotal role in imparting education and Teachers Training Programs through Cluster Based Training (CBT), School Leadership Development Program (SLDP) and Teaching in Clusters by Subject Specialists (TICSS)”.

Robertson (1996 quoted in Javed, et al 2012) stated that the teachers who possess professional and interpersonal skills are more effective in their classrooms in terms of behaviour, attitude and achievement. Teachers training programs need re-evaluation and reorganization to remove the deficiencies (Javed, et al 2012).

Nadeem (2013) has stressed on the role of EFL teacher through interactive approach at public sector schools in which he has recommended the adoption of interactive mode of teaching in all EFL levels especially at the public sector schools. But the question arises whether this interaction is possible between the two parties (teachers and students) i.e. the teacher’s role yet needs to be decided. In the present study, the researcher has tried to investigate the problems that hinder the way of defining a teacher’s role.

Methodology

Participants

There were 360 school teachers of different districts of Punjab who participated in this study. The participants were 213 males and 147 females (189 urban and 171 rural). The participants were aged between 23 – 48 years.

Figure 1: Gender and Location of the Participants

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Where do you live?	City	116	73	189
	village	97	74	171
Total		213	147	360

Table 1: Gender and Location of the Participants

Research Tool

The researcher devised a questionnaire to know about the opinion of the teachers regarding doing different duties other than teaching and about teacher training. The questionnaire was sent to experts at Baha-ud-Din Zakariya University, Multan and The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The experts suggested a few amendments. The questionnaire consisted of 20 items on five point liker scale (from strongly agree to strongly disagree) and the Cronbach's Alpha for the questionnaire was also calculated that was found as .899.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

The questionnaire was administered to the teachers at different schools in Punjab. The data was collected in a quite informal way. The teachers were told about the purpose of the research and they were told that their participation was voluntary. It took 20 minutes to collect data from every school. After collection the data was analysed by using SPSS version XIV.

Results and Discussion

The frequencies of the respondents were computed for each of the questionnaire items. After the data analysis the following results have been found. It was found that 318 teachers were agreeing with the statement that they were satisfied with their job. This should be clear that this satisfaction with the job was just in terms of employment i.e. the teachers were satisfied in the sense that at least they had a job in an environment in which it was almost impossible to survive without a job. Most of the teachers (183) disagreed with the statement that they were happy to do other than teaching jobs. It means majority

of the teachers do not like to do such extra jobs. There were 228 teachers who were not happy to go for election duties, 271 participants disagreed that they were happy to go for basic health programme duties, 310 teachers disagreed that they were not happy to go to collect data for census. The result of these three items clearly indicates that teachers are neither willing nor happy to do other than teaching jobs. 174 teachers were satisfied with the teacher training programmes and 131 disagreed with the statement whereas 55 teachers didn't give any opinion. This shows majority of the teachers are satisfied with the training programmes but later on they explained the reason behind this satisfaction was to leave the school and enjoy the training programmes where they could find refreshments and sometimes dailies (money per day). About professional development item 305 participants strongly disagreed with the statement that teacher training programmes provided them up to date information for their professional development and 335 participants disagreed with the statement that these training programmes polish their professional skills. 231 teachers disagreed that they would love to participate in teacher training programme. Just 78 participants were agree to participate in training programmes and 51 had no opinion about participating in teacher training programmes. 99 teachers agreed that in-service training paves the way for teaching in a better way whereas 196 participants disagreed with the statement. 227 teachers disagreed that the training programmes were in line with their teaching system and 125 agreed with the statement. 260 teachers disagreed with the statement that teachers should do the menial jobs whereas 98 teachers agreed with the statement. 323 participants agreed that there should be proper staff for the menial jobs i.e. teachers didn't want to do these menial

jobs in place of other staff because these menial jobs do not suit their temperament and they didn't feel easy in doing these jobs. 226 participants disagreed that these menial jobs provided them with the opportunities to polish their professional skills. 314 participants strongly disagreed with the statement that menial jobs helped them in their professional duties. 251 participants strongly disagreed and 51 disagreed with the statement that the teachers should be assigned the menial jobs. 33 participants strongly agreed and 20 agreed with the statement just because of some other reasons that may be explained later. 213 teachers disagreed and 126 agreed with the statement that teachers should be happy with the menial jobs because these give them extra money. 248 participants disagreed and 86 agreed with the statement that teachers were provided with all the teaching facilities at schools. 209 teachers disagreed and 141 agreed with the statement that school administration supported teachers in their professional development. 247 participants strongly agreed and 76 agreed with the final statement that the authorities forced the teachers to do extra duties other than teaching. This is so because the teachers are threatened by the authorities that they would be rendered jobless if they didn't do said duties. So the teachers have to do this even against their own will.

The study supports Robertson's study (1996) that the teachers with professional and interpersonal skills can be more effective in that it has been noted that neither the training programmes nor the school administration give any help in teachers' professional development. The result of the questionnaire analyzed clearly indicates that the training programmes and the menial jobs do not provide any stance or support in teachers' professional skills or their professional development.

The quality of teacher training programmes has an imbalance as they lack harmony with the school system and need to improve by revising the curriculum according to the needs of changing culture and the demands of the modern world (Ahmed, 2009). Now the question arises that in such a lame and creeping environment how is it possible to produce quality teachers and quality education where the authorities are pushing the teaching staff in all other tasks rather than in teaching. The study

clearly alarms that the situation may get the worst in the coming years if there could be no remedial measures in this regard.

According to Saeed et al (2013) teachers are found weak in solving students' academic and social problems. Teachers are weak just because of lack of proper professional training. In the teacher training programmes they just come to make sure their presence in order to get their refreshments and some honorarium to attend these training programmes. This research shows that the situation is really worse just because of wrong policies and wrong direction provided to the teachers by the authorities.

Pedagogical Implications and Recommendations

- Teacher's role must be defined in categorical terms so that he may know his role and his professional responsibilities and may perform his duty effectively and honestly.
- To ensure the interest and enhance the motivation of teachers in the teaching profession government should increase the facilities for teachers and it should provide professional skills at institutional level.
- It is very essential that an environment of professionalism should be given to the teachers and to the institutions so that there may develop their professional skills.
- Teachers should be given the job surety so that they may take full interest in their professional tasks.
- There must be a separated staff for the menial jobs so that the teachers may justify their teaching.
- Teachers should be given a very handsome salary package so that they may not look for ways and means to earn more from other menial jobs because some of the teachers prefer to do these extra jobs just because the sake of money and the other thing is that they try to avoid teaching because they don't want to teach.

- All the educational institutions should make serious and honest efforts to equip the teachers with teaching skills and should increase their professional attitude as well.
- The problems can be solved by providing teaching and learning resources to schools, providing particular professional development opportunities and incentives to teachers at all levels.
- Training is imparted that's a good thing but the training is never up to the modern international standards which need to be revised.
- The research suggests 'teachers training programmes need reevaluation and reorganization to remove the deficiencies' and to make these programmes more profession oriented and more effective.

Conclusion

It is our dilemma that highly qualified teachers are recruited in teaching at primary level and even after that they are forced by the authorities to do these menial jobs. This study particularly focused on the multiple roles of teachers (both male and female) in the Punjab. The study serves two purposes i.e. on the one hand it stresses on defining the role of a teacher with regard to his profession and duties and on the other hand it could be useful for educational policy makers and educational institutions to rectify the problems which the teachers have to face in their professional development. The study can be further extended to other areas of Pakistan also.

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Appendix (A) Questionnaire

Kindly encircle the statements with the most suitable answers.

Name: _____

Gender: _____

Institution Name: _____

Age: _____

Teaching Experience: _____

1. I am quite satisfied with my job.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

2. I am happy to do the job other than teaching.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

3. I am happy to go for election duties.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

4. I am happy to go for basic health programme duties.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

5. I am happy to go to collect data for census.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

6. I am satisfied with the teacher training programmes.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

7. Teacher training programmes provide us up to date information for our professional development.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

8. Teacher training programmes polish our professional skills.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

9. I would love to participate in teacher training programmes.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

10. In service training paves the way for better teaching methods.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

11. Teacher training programmes are in line with our education system.

Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

12. Teacher should do the menial jobs other than teaching.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

13. There should be proper staff for the menial jobs.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

14. Menial jobs provide opportunities to polish our professional skills.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

15. Menial jobs are helpful in our professional duties.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

16. Teachers should be assigned the menial jobs.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

17. Teachers should be happy with the menial jobs because these give them extra money.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

18. Teachers are provided with all the teaching facilities at schools.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

19. School administration supports the teachers in their professional development.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

20. The authorities force the teachers to do extra duties other than teaching.
Strongly agree Agree No Opinion
Disagree Strongly disagree

Appendix (B) Mean score and Frequencies

	Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SA	A	NO	D	SD
1	I am quite satisfied with my job.	360	4.30	.738	159	159	33	9	0
2	I am happy to do the job other than teaching.	360	2.82	1.577	75	82	20	70	113
3	I am happy to go for election duties.	360	2.31	1.389	37	51	44	82	146
4	I am happy to go for basic health programme duties.	360	1.69	1.077	7	23	59	35	236
5	I am happy to go to collect data for census.	360	1.41	.912	4	18	28	20	290
6	I am satisfied with the teacher training programmes.	360	3.01	1.556	75	99	55	18	113
7	Teacher training programmes provide us up to date information for our professional development.	360	1.35	.946	14	8	12	21	305
8	Teacher training programmes polish our professional skills.	360	1.33	.657	1	4	20	61	274
9	I would love to participate in teacher training programmes.	360	2.17	1.462	45	33	51	41	190
10	In-service training paves the way for better teaching methods.	360	2.42	1.404	32	69	63	51	145
11	Teacher training programmes are in line with our education system.	360	2.44	1.656	75	50	8	54	173
12	Teacher should do the menial jobs other than teaching.	360	2.13	1.587	62	34	4	48	212
13	There should be proper staff for the menial jobs.	360	4.36	.856	190	133	18	14	5
14	Menial jobs provide us opportunities to polish our professional skills.	360	1.49	1.015	16	13	5	65	261
15	Menial jobs are helpful in our professional duties.	360	1.39	1.091	22	12	3	9	314
16	Teachers should be assigned the menial jobs.	360	1.70	1.291	33	20	3	53	251
17	Teachers should be happy with the menial jobs because these give them extra money.	360	2.47	1.607	63	63	21	46	167
18	Teachers are provided with all the teaching facilities at schools.	360	1.99	1.445	30	56	26	18	230
19	School administration supports teachers in their professional development.	360	2.47	1.682	66	75	10	19	190
20	The authorities force the teachers to do extra duties other than teaching.	360	4.51	.893	247	76	14	18	5